

Advanced and Late Medieval Irrigation Farming of Jizzakh Oasis

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Abstract:

This article talks about the history of advanced and late medieval irrigated agriculture of Jizzakh oasis, its important aspects. The history of irrigated agriculture of the region was clarified by analyzing the valuable information about the irrigation system in the oasis and the results of the research conducted in the archaeological monuments in the works of the medieval historians.

Keywords: Ustrushana country, Jizzakh oasis, medieval historians, irrigation canals, Bunjikat, Sangzar, Kaliyatepa, Orda, Zamin, Babur, Abdullah Khan II, Khanbandi, Tuyatortar canal.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the interesting history of the Jizzakh oasis, which formed the north-western borders of the ancient Ustrushona country, has been carried out quite intensively in recent years. The ancient history of the Jizzakh oasis - the processes of anthropogenesis, the history of the primitive community system, the culture of urban development, the history of rural areas, the culture of sedentary farmers and herders, its irrigated agriculture, its emergence, formation, There is also a lot of research going on about the specifics. It is known from the history of mankind that agriculture and artificial irrigation farms were created in the Stone Age and are being improved and formed in the following periods. In this article, the formation of irrigated agriculture and its specific features are considered on the example of Jizzakh oasis. The irrigated agriculture of the Jizzakh oasis in the ancient and early Middle Ages was well formed and developed in the later Middle Ages, based on the requirements of time and space, as well as innovations.

MAIN PART

We have at our disposal not only well-dated archeological monuments, but also, in some cases, contradictory evidences, to give an idea of the advanced and late medieval irrigated agriculture and irrigation networks of the Jizzakh oasis. there are written records of medieval Arabic authors.

According to the medieval geographers-travelers, during this period, Ustrushana became a developed multi-branch agricultural region like Sogd, Fergana, Shash regions of Movarunnahr.

As Istakhri writes about these regions ... “there is no city, village, field or pasture without water supply. They have the cleanest, softest, and most delicious water”. And Ibn-Hawkal reports that fruits are grown in abundance in this country, and even “feeds domestic animals” with fruits. According to written and archeological data, during this period, the Ustrushana people were mainly engaged in grain farming - wheat, barley, oats, rice, sesame, peas, beans, and horticulture - grapes, apricots, apples, cherries[Pardaev, Suyunov..., 1999, p.232-233]. Those who grew peaches, walnuts, almonds, melons, watermelons, and pumpkins in the field of agriculture. Cotton cultivation has an important place in the agricultural economy.

It can be seen that the basis of the crops was formed by plants and fruits that require a lot of water. Unfortunately, the authors of medieval written sources did not write down accurate and complete information about the irrigation systems of Ustrushana. Although the authors provide relatively complete information about the water supply of the capital Bunjikat, they only briefly and generally mention that there is a “running water source” about the water management of the rest of the villages and their capital cities.

By the way, Istakhri reports that there are no rivers and lakes where ships can sail in Ustrushana, while Yakut informs about Zamin’s “abundant running water, endless grain fields, orchards, and countless livestock”. The unknown author of “Khudud al-Alam” describes Jizzakh as “a city near running water”. It is worth noting that even from these short confessions of tourists, it is possible to know that in the Middle Ages in Ustrushana, in particular, in its north-western villages, there were extensive irrigation systems, and abundant harvests were obtained in irrigated agriculture. Agricultural products grown in Ustrushana were sold in the neighboring regions, in particular, in Khojand markets[Pardaev, Pardaev, Khasanboev, 2021. P.696-703].

The results of archeological researches show that during this period, the number of living spaces of the population decreased compared to the early Middle Ages, but the private area of the spaces, the areas under their control, and the agricultural areas were significantly expanded. This situation is first of all reflected in the irrigated farming oases of the lower Sangzar oasis of north-western Ustrushana. In particular, during this period, the farming areas in the Jizzakh oasis expanded to the borders of the desert-steppe regions. In the first quarter of the 9th century, hundreds of hectares of land were put into agricultural circulation due to the Khudaisar rabad, built by Afshin Haidar ibn Kavus, the crown prince of Ustrushna, on the border of the northern desert-steppe[Suyunov,1999. p. 29-30].

Medieval authors describe Khudaisar as one of the most beautiful, large and famous rabads of Movarounnakh. Rabad was provided with a water source, and there were various community and foundation lands around it. A ditch was drawn from Sangzor for the water supply of Khudaisar Rabadi. The total length is 15 km. Today, a dry riverbed called Uruqulisoi and the “Kok Ravat” monument on its shore have been preserved from this stream, which reached[Pardaev, Suyunov..., 1999, p.234].

The lands of the Kaliyatepa irrigation canal expanded to the east in the 9th-12th centuries. Molkanlik stream is 1.5 km from Kaliyatepa. It reaches the “Toptolota” area located in the east. IX-XII: XIV-XVI from around the holy place of “Toptolota”; The discovery of many pottery vessels of the 17th-19th centuries confirms these opinions.

Orda’s irrigation system is fully formed during this period, and its irrigated agricultural land extends to Kattatepa (3.74 ha.), Sarayliktepa (2.24 ha.), Ilonlitepa (2. 25 ha.) in the 9th-12th centuries in the basin of the “Yakhtanlik” brook, it expands as an example of rural areas and their agricultural plots. In the development of irrigated agriculture in the Middle Ages, excellent irrigation facilities and

universal hydrotechnical knowledge were of great importance in their construction [Anarbaev, 1970, p. 25].

In connection with the construction of the classic Khanbandi dam built in the 10th century on the basis of the existing methods and traditions of the construction of hydrotechnical structures of Central Asia, another Kaltepa irrigation district will be created on the northern slope of the Nurota mountains. 1500 hectares on the borders of Kyzylkum and Mirzachol in the 10th-12th centuries through these irrigation networks [Mukhammadjanov, 1972, p.375]. water is released to the ground. During this period, the processes of expansion of irrigated farming areas are also observed in the irrigation regions that were created in the early Middle Ages in the middle and upper reaches of the Zaminsuv, Khojamushkentsoi, and Sangzar basins.

The invasion of the Mongols and their rule for a century and a half brought the economic and cultural life of Central Asia, including Ustrushana, to a deep crisis, especially agriculture and irrigation networks. It destroyed the irrigation districts that have been operating for several centuries.

Special attention was paid to the agricultural economy of the north-western Ustrushana, including the Jizzakh oasis, during the period of the owner Amir Temur and the Timurids (XIV-XV centuries). The old branch ditch and auxiliary ditches are re-excavated and resume their previous activity. The city addresses of Kaliyatepa and Orda will be restored, and the land around them will be used. The territory of Jizzakh oasis is rapidly regaining its previous position in the political and economic life of the country [Suyunov, 1999. p. 59-61]. Because the oasis of Jizzakh in north-western Ustrushana has long been the “eastern gate” of great military strategic importance for Samarkand Sogd.

In the time of Mirzo Ulugbek (1409-1449), the Timurid ruler of Samarkand, special attention was paid to Jizzakh oasis. Because Ulugbek’s rule coincides with the period of activation of opposition forces against the Timurids in Tashkent, Yettisuv, Mongolia. For this reason, the fortifications of the cities of Kaliyatepa, Orda and Moltoptepa will be repaired quickly, and economic works will be started.

Babur Mirza’s reminiscences: “In Dizak... fatty meats and small cuts are cheap, sweet melons and good grapes are plentiful... we got rid of hunger and reached the comfort of safety and the comfort of cheapness” [Babur, 1989, p.86]. One can imagine the results of the above creative works. In North-West Ustrushana, in this period, unlike Jizzakh, Zomin is very slowly growing in its old place, but it cannot restore its position in the past. Sabat cannot recover from the new one in its place and moved to the right bank of Khojamushkentsoi as a small village. It is not recorded in written sources after the 16th century. The historical fate of the village of Kharakana is the same.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Even during the rule of the Shaybanites in the 16th century, the Jizzakh oasis of northwestern Ustrushana was used as a large administrative center and a particularly convenient military base. As a result of Shaybani Khan’s campaigns, most of the Uzbek clans from Dashti Kipchak settled in the Jizzakh oasis, the demographics of the population increased sharply, there was a need to develop new arable land and provide water for it.

During the reign of Bukhara Khan Abdulla Khan II (1556-1598), the water supply of the Jizzakh oasis and agriculture was greatly improved with the construction of the Tuyatortar branch canal with a total length of 97 km starting from the Ravotkhoja dam of Zarafshan. During this period, the “Five Pipes” water separator was built in the area of the current city of Jizzakh downstream of Sangzor, and 12 canals named after the 12 dahas of Jizzakh received water from this water separator [Pardaev, Suyunov, 1993, p.49-50].

Since the early days of Central Asian khanates, the north-western regions of Ustrushana have been under the control of the Bukhara Emirate. Orda is the administrative center of the Jizzakh Province, which is part of the Bukhara Emirate. During this period, the total area is 100 ha. Crowded neighborhoods are emerging around this city, which has approached. According to information, during this period, the development of the desert-steppe areas of the northern regions of the oasis continued. Farmers spent a long time in the field during the planting and harvesting season and returned to Orde only in the winter months[Pardaev, Pardaev, 1999, p.73].

Kaliyatepa and Orda irrigation sub-districts are combined in this period to form a single irrigation district. As the population grows, the shortage of land in these two ancient farming areas, especially in the Kaliyatepa zone, begins to be strongly felt. Part of the population around Kaliyatepa moved to the desert-steppe lands of the oasis. Nowadays, there are “Kaliya-Molkanlik” and “Chol Molkanlik” neighborhoods in Jizzakh, which confirm these ethnographic data[Pardaev, Suyunov..., 1999, p.236]. Thus, according to archeological researches, according to written sources, irrigated agriculture was formed in the north-western Ustrushana, as well as in other regions of the Turan-Turkistan region, from ancient times and has a long history of its development crossed the line.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the mountain and sub-mountain areas of the Jizzakh oasis, located in the central part of Uzbekistan, which formed the northern and northwestern borders of Ustrushana in the past, have long been among the densely populated historical cultural lands. In addition to dry farming in large and small valleys formed in the basin of Sangzar and Zaminsuv rivers, numerous streams and springs, agriculture and settled life based on artificial irrigation systems began a long time ago. Also, in the desert-steppe region Mirzachol, located on the northern and northwestern borders of the oasis, the activity of nomadic herders in the archaic, antique and early middle ages was reflected in the archaeological materials. Taking into account the material and cultural samples of Neolithic and Bronze Age communities recorded in these areas, it is possible to confirm that human habitation and economic activities have been established in this wonderful historical and cultural region for a long time.

The history of the developed and late medieval irrigated agriculture of the Jizzakh oasis was given by comparing the results of excavations conducted in archaeological monuments based on the information provided by Arab tourists. Irrigation facilities and spaces in the oasis were studied, divided into irrigation districts. Thoughts were given about water facilities, their construction history, possibilities and advantages, which had a good effect on irrigated agriculture in the developed Middle Ages. During the last middle ages, including Amir Timur and the Timurids, the activities of irrigated agriculture in this area, the role of the people in the activities, the condition of the water structures, their inefficiency, suspension of their activities, etc. development processes in this area were analyzed based on existing written sources and archaeological materials.

REFERENCES.

1. Pardaev M., Suyunov S., Pardaev A. The emergence and stages of development of irrigated agriculture in North-West Ustrushana // Journal of the history of material culture of Uzbekistan-30 issue. Samarkand. 1999.
2. Pardaev M., Suyunov S. From the history of irrigation of North-West Ustrushana. // Uzbekistan in ancient and medieval times. Statement of lectures. Samarkand. 1993.
3. Pardaev M., Pardaev A, Jizzakh in the late Middle Ages. // Sugd in the system of cultural relations of Central Asia. Statement of lectures. Samarkand. 1999.
4. Mukhamadjanov A. The history of the irrigation of the Lower Zarafshan oasis (from ancient times to the beginning of the 20th century). Tashkent. 1972.

5. Babur Zakhiriddin Mukhammad. Baburnama. Tashkent. 1989.
6. Pardaev M., Pardaev A., Khasanboev T. From the history of ancient irrigation systems of Jizzakh oasis. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. 2021.
7. Anarbaev S. From the history of watering the Jizzakh oasis. "Truth of Syrdarya", November 26, 1970. 1987.
8. Suyunov S. Irrigation history of northwestern Ustrushana (based on archaeological materials of the 5th-16th centuries). Dissertation manuscript. Samarkand. 1999.